

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_1_3	
Title	<i>Instorier</i>
Category	Socio-cultural (for Eidsvika and Ghostfishing)
Purpose of the method	<i>It is a storytelling tool, which allows an engaging dissemination of the background and aims of the case study for the public.</i>
Effort in time	<i>Depending on the complexity of the story it requires between 4- 15 hours of work to create a story.?</i>
Number of objects investigated	N/A
Data format	<i>textual, images, videos, maps</i>
Description	<i>Instorier is a digital storytelling tool which can be used by people without graphical or coding background. It is a user-friendly tool which creates powerful visual outputs. It is possible to include maps and interactive formats within the stories.</i>
Basic Literature	<i>Time to learn. Instorier. https://instorier.com/learn</i>
Contact person within the project	<i>David Herbert, David.herbet@uib.no, Leader Case Study Bergen Instorier is currently being developed for collaborative education and scientific communication use through a pilot project at the University of Bergen. If you join the pilot by 30 June 2025, you will be eligible for free lifetime basic use of the tool. Please contact David at the mail above if you wish to participate or for further information.</i>
Linked material	<p><i>Most helpful ressources:</i></p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jVU3sv-Pzw4 (this is a really short (1 minute) introduction to making a story)</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zdly83F7Vbl (this is a 6-minute introduction to the editing tools)</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WUWnBPViPt8 (this is an 8-minute guide to creating 3D scenes)</p> <p><i>Comprehensive list of tutorial provided by Instorier:</i> https://instorier.com/learn</p>